

The Products of the Reaction between Hydrated Ferric Oxide and Perchloric Acid Mixed in Different Molar Proportions. Part II : Isolation of a Polymeric Ferric Perchlorate Compound and the Effects of Acids and Salts on the Spectra of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$ Species

S. P. MOULIK & K. K. SEN GUPTA

Department of Physical Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-32

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An apparently acid insoluble (but water soluble) dirty yellow polymeric hydroxo ferric perchlorate has been isolated. The spectral characteristics of this compound in water and in mild acid have been reported. The association of ClO_4^- with $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$ has been clearly evidenced. The true dissociation constants of the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2\text{ClO}_4$ salts have been evaluated. A systematic study of the effects of different acids and their salts on $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ under identical experimental conditions has also been made.

In literature¹⁻⁶ there appear considerable investigations on the interaction of anions with ferric ion. A systematic study is, however, rare covering such anion effects on a particular hydroxo species under identical experimental conditions. In our early publications⁷⁻⁹ preparation of ferric ion species have been described. In this writing, we mention isolation of a special sample and a detailed study of the perchlorates of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$ species. The effects of acids and salts on the same have also been reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals used were either E. Merck, G.R. or B.D.H., AnalaR grades. For the preparation of the initial ferric perchlorate we refer to our previous papers⁷⁻⁹. Some of these samples were colloidal and some were clear solutions. The colloidal solutions, on standing, gave a dirty yellow precipitate. This readily dissolves in water giving a clear yellow solution but is precipitated on addition of acid. From this solution a pinkish material can be crystallized which is the $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ salt. The other solutions used for the acid and salt effects on the absorption spectra were sample 5* (containing mostly $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ species) and sample 3* (containing mostly $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$ species) reported in Part I. Spectral measurements were taken in a Beckman DB apparatus using silica cuvetts of 1 cm. thickness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Spectral characteristics of the isolated sample : The results are shown in Figure 1. The dirty yellow polymeric compound (curve 1) has two broad bands, one around 285 nm and another around 365 nm. In 0.2% perchloric acid it gives a turbid solution, whose curve

(no. 2) is monotonous in nature. This compound is presumably a polymeric hydroxo-ferric perchlorate whose composition is yet unknown. In this figure curves 3 and 4 refer to $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^+_{2}$ spectra, which in presence of $1M \text{HClO}_4$ get converted into Fe^{3+} ion (curve 5).

Fig. 1 : Absorption spectra of different ferric perchlorate salts at $1 \times 10^{-4}M$ 1 : Compound I in water; 2 : Compound I in $0.2M \text{HClO}_4$; 3 : Compound III in water; 4 : Compound II in water; 5 : Compounds II & III in $1M \text{HClO}_4$.

Association of ClO_4^- with $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^+_{2}$: In past works, physicochemical studies were made in presence of swamping concentrations of NaClO_4 (usually $3M$, ClO_4^- being the least complexing) to calculate the classical equilibrium constants, etc. However, the association and the dissociation phenomena between the pairs of species $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ and

Fig. 2 : Effect of NaClO_4 on the spectra of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2\text{ClO}_4$ in water at $1 \times 10^{-4}M$. 1 : $\mu = 0$; 2 : $\mu = 0.025$; 3 : $\mu = 0.05$; 4 : $\mu = 0.10$; 5 : $\mu = 0.20$; 6 : $\mu = 0.30$; 7 : $\mu = 0.50$.

ClO_4^- , and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$ and ClO_4^- may be an interesting aspect of study. Actually, ClO_4^- ion has got remarkable effect on the absorption spectra of the hydroxo ferric species. A look into the Figs. 3 and 4 corroborates this fact. For the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$ species, the spectral shift was not always in one direction up to $\mu = 0.05$. The monotonous nature of the two

Fig. 3 : Effect of NaClO_4 on the spectra of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ in water at $1 \times 10^{-4} M$. 1 : $\mu = 0$; 2 : $\mu = 0.025$; 3 : $\mu = 0.05$; 4 : $\mu = 0.10$; 5 : $\mu = 0.20$; 6 : $\mu = 0.30$; 7 : $\mu = 0.50$; 8 : $\mu = 1.0$.

curves also existed upto this ionic strength. This is presumably due to the depolymerizing effect of the added salt. For higher ionic strengths a definite order is observed. For the other species, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$, the spectral shift is nicely in order. Appearance of almost an isobestic point infers the existence of mainly one type of hydroxo species throughout the ionic

Fig. 4 : Absorption spectra of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$ at $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ in presence of mineral acids. 1 : $1 M \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$; 2 : $0.1 M \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$; 3 : $1 M \text{HClO}_4$; 4 : $0.1 M \text{HClO}_4$; 5 : $1 M \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$; 6 : $0.1 M \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$; 7 : $1 M \text{HCl}$; 8 : $0.1 M \text{HCl}$; 9 : $0.1 M \text{HNO}_3$.

strength range. Complete disappearance of the maximum around 300 nm, and appearance of a minimum in that position, at the highest perchlorate ion concentration, is a remarkable feature. Down after 275 nm, significant increase in the optical density is observed.

In this writing, assuming a dissociation suppression phenomenon, respective dissociation constants of the hydroxo ferric perchlorate salts have been calculated from the spectral data. We take for granted that in solution at $1 \times 10^{-4} M$, the species $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$ exist being completely dissociated from their co-partner, ClO_4^- ions. Now addition of perchlorate ion suppresses the dissociation, and at $\mu = 0.5$ the suppression is complete.

Now at any wavelength below 275 nm, say at 240 nm, the spectral rise at any ionic strength has been considered as to the formation extent of the unionised salt. Then knowing the extinctions of the ionized species and calculating that of the unionized salt (by dividing the optical density of the sample at $\mu = 0.5$ by the ferric concentration), finally the concentrations of both the ionized and the unionized species for all the ionic strengths have been computed¹⁰. In Table I the values of these dissociation constants are given as a function of the ionic strengths. The change of the spectral pattern, therefore, tells how a free and a perchlorate bound hydroxo ferric species can spectrally behave. In Table I, the zero ionic strength values are extrapolated ones from the nice straight line plots between $\log K$ and μ . These are therefore the true K values.

TABLE I

Dissociation constants of the hydroxo ferric perchlorates

Ionic strength (μ)	K	
	\leftarrow $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{ClO}_4)_2$	\rightarrow $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2\text{ClO}_4$
0.0	$10^{-7.50}$	$10^{-3.90}$
0.025	$10^{-7.80}$	—
0.05	$10^{-8.00}$	—
0.10	$10^{-8.46}$	$10^{-4.30}$
0.20	$10^{-9.16}$	$10^{-4.62}$
0.30	$10^{-9.86}$	$10^{-5.72}$
0.50	$10^{-12.62}$	$10^{-6.60}$

Effects of acids and salts on the absorption spectra of $Fe(OH)(ClO_4)_2$: We selected this hydroxo ferric perchlorate species with a view to study systematically the effects of acids and their salts under identical experimental conditions. In Fig. 4, the effects of the acids at two concentrations (0.1 *M* and 1*M*) are depicted. It is quite natural that the acids will replace the perchlorate anion by their conjugate anion, and the OH^- ligand will be replaced by water formation with their H^+ ions. It is evident from the figure that such a reaction in 0.1*M* acid is incomplete²⁷ because in all cases a prominent maximum is formed in 1*M* acid.

The interactions of the anions with $Fe(OH)^{2+}$ species will be discussed with reference to the $Fe(OH)(ClO_4)_2$ spectra. A comparison between the acids and their salts is shown in Fig. 5. The spectral shift is obviously dependent upon the strength of the ligands concerned. This order in the present case is $HClO_4 > H_3PO_4 > HNO_3 > H_2SO_4 > HCl$. From the electronegativity standpoint this order¹¹ should be $HClO_4 > H_2SO_4 > HCl > H_3PO_4$. In our case this order is followed for the first three acids. Since NO_3^- has got appreciable absorption and we could not use concentrated HNO_3 or $NaNO_3$, nothing can be said, even apparently, about this anion. Therefore, the exception is H_3PO_4 or KH_2PO_4 , which at 1*M* strength probably contribute similar anion, $H_2PO_4^-$. Now chloride ion can form different complexes² with Fe^{3+} , and therefore, for any conclusion, proper choice of the species that has been formed in solution should be made. According to Gamlen and Jordan⁴ evidences for more than one λ_{max} for ferric chloride ($FeCl_3$) complex were observed at acidities not less than 8.65 *M*. A 250 nm shoulder and two maxima at nearly 340 nm (sharp) and 400 nm were reported by these authors. In the present study, a shoulder at 250 nm and a band at 340 nm have been observed. This should be characteristics of $FeCl_3$. Since we have worked at 1*M* HCl (much less than that used by Gamlen and Jordan) there should be a good possibility of $FeCl_3$ to be much less stable. Formation of other species, $FeCl^{2+}$ and $FeCl_2^+$ are also possible. At moderate acidities, all these species have maximum⁴ at 340 nm, which probably fixes the chloride after $SO_4^{=}$ in the spectral order.

Fig. 5: Absorption spectra of $Fe(OH)^{2+}$ at $1 \times 10^{-4}M$ in acids (1*M*) and salts ($\mu = 1$). 1: without acid or salt; 2: H_3PO_4 ; 3: KH_2PO_4 ; 4: H_2SO_4 ; 5: K_2SO_4 ; 6: $HClO_4$; 7: $NaClO_4$; 8: HCl ; 9: KCl .

The addition of salts to the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ solution decreased the optical densities apparently in all the cases. A shift of the maximum absorption band is also noticed. On the other hand, the absorption of the solutions in presence of sulphate ions is very low. This is in agreement with the observations already made⁵ that sulphate complex of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ in absence of H_2SO_4 would have very little absorption. Now the significant difference between the spectra in presence of acids and their salts can be attributed to two types of complex formation.

Therefore, the role of $p\text{H}$ should be very critically judged before any comparison is made of the effects of anions on the ferric ion. Since stabilization of Fe^{3+} is practically impossible except in strong acid, no such comparison is worthy neglecting the involvement of either the H^+ or the A^- ions. In the course of this study, similar effects have been found on the other hydroxo ferric species, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{+2}$. The onward replacement of the anion, ClO_4^- from the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ by other anions, of the salts of the acids used, has also been done working at different ionic strengths. A shift of the absorption band has been definitely observed in some cases. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Effects of anions on the λ_{max} of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ salt.

Conc. = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$; λ_{max} at $\mu = 0$ is 295 nm

Ionic strength (μ)	$\lambda_{max}(\text{nm})$		
	Cl^-	H_2PO_4^-	NO_3^-
0.1	295	260-265	256
0.2	295	270(b)	—
0.3	—	—	—
0.4	300(b)	270(b)	—
0.5	—	—	—
0.6	320(b)	270(b)	—
1.0	320(b)	270(s)	—

For all ionic strengths λ_{max} for $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ species disappeared in sulphate as well as in perchlorate solutions. In the case of perchlorate ion there occurred a tendency of a shoulder at 240 nm which became prominent at $\mu = 0.5$. For the nitrate ions, measurements at higher ionic strengths were omitted due to appreciable absorbancy of this anion.

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